

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL WORKERS IN PROMOTING SELF-FULFILLMENT AMONG OLDER PEOPLE

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Abstract

The aging population and the increasing number of elderly people mean, older people face a variety of problems: changing health, past events and losses, narrowing of social ties, changes in social roles, negative social attitudes and personal characteristics. Old age is the last stage of a person's life, which is conducive to self-fulfillment and is synonymous with self-care, and it is important for a person to feel that his or her life still has a sense of purpose in order to live a more active and productive life, in a way that takes into account the person and the possibilities available to him or her. However, the implementation of this process is often limited by social isolation, health problems, economic difficulties, and age discrimination. Therefore, the work of social workers becomes not only a means of assistance, but also a means of empowerment, allowing older people to remain active, independent, and meaningful to society.

Keywords. Old people, self-fulfillment, social work, roles of a social worker.

Introduction

Data from the World Health Organization [14] show that in 2050, people aged 60 and older will make up 2.1 billion of the total population worldwide. According to data from the Official Statistics Portal [8], in 2023, people aged 65 and older accounted for 20% of the population of Lithuania (571,700), and since 2013, the number of elderly people has increased by as much as 5.4% (29,500). For older people, self-fulfillment takes on a specific meaning – it is associated with the ability to maintain dignity, participate in social life, pass on experience to the younger generation, continue favorite activities, or volunteer [5]. However, the implementation of this process is often limited by social isolation, health problems, economic difficulties, and age discrimination. Therefore, the work of social workers becomes not only a means of assistance, but also a means of empowerment, allowing older people to remain active, independent, and meaningful to society.

Social workers become an important link between individual needs, social structures, and the social services system, operating in various contexts—individual, group, and community. Therefore, it is necessary to reveal the roles that social workers perform and how these roles contribute to ensuring the self-realization of older people. Specialists help them to understand and accept the ageing process and its consequences in order to achieve positive ageing, developing the ability to use their time productively for self-realisation, maintaining emotional stability, inner cohesion, opportunities for personal development and a meaningful perception of life [7; 13; 9; 4]. It is not only the task of social workers,

but also of society as a whole to provide older people with opportunities for self-realization, continuous personal development, and certain social commitments [2].

Research results show [13] that social work specialists involve elderly people in certain activities by applying selected professional roles. Professional roles can be applied in various capacities, such as teacher, listener, advisor, protector, etc. The socio-cultural activities organized are based on the social worker's empathy, friendliness, sincerity, and openness, while maintaining the principles of confidentiality.

Thus, social workers play an important role in encouraging older people to find purpose, meaning, and fulfillment in their lives. They provide social services and emotional support to help older adults discover their potential. Social workers can also organize activities that promote socialization, activity, and community involvement, thereby encouraging older adults to pursue meaningful goals and find meaning in life. Their role is important because they can help older people overcome challenges, solve problems, and enhance their self-esteem and quality of life.

Research objective. To reveal the roles of social workers in promoting self-realization among older people.

Research methods. Analysis of scientific literature, semi-structured interviews, qualitative content analysis.

Research methodology

Type of research. In order to reveal the roles of social workers in working with elderly people to

achieve their self-realization, a qualitative data collection method was used, and the research method was a semi-structured interview. The basis of the research is focused on the views, personal attitudes, and everyday lives of the research participants [6].

Sample. The research sample was selected using precise selection criteria – social workers. Social workers working in nursing homes and social services day centers were selected and participated in the research. Six social workers working with elderly people participated in the research.

Research instrument. The semi-structured interview questions are divided into three categories. The first category consists of five questions focused on factors influencing self-actualization and the search for meaning in life among older adults. The second category consists of five questions aimed at revealing the sources of meaning in life for older people. The third category consists of six questions aimed at finding

out about the role of social workers in promoting self-realization among older people. This article will present the results of the research focused on the roles of social workers.

Research ethics. This research was conducted in accordance with the principles of research ethics: free choice to participate in the research, goodwill, and confidentiality.

Research results

Self-actualization in older adults. The results of the research revealed that self-actualization in older adults is a highly individual process that is directly related to a person's values. Self-realization can be influenced by one or more factors, such as finding and developing meaningful activities, maintaining close relationships, continuous improvement, involvement in the community, and continuing to engage in favorite activities in old age (see Table 1).

Table 1

Social worker's understanding of self-realization in old age among elderly people

Category	Subcategory
Factors influencing self-actualization in older adults	Meaningful activities
	Relationships with loved ones
	Knowledge
	Integration into the community
	Continuation of favorite activities in old age
	Individuality of self-realization
	The most important human values

The results of this research also showed that self-realization can be very diverse and understood differently. Self-realization manifests itself through a person's individuality and meaningful activities, relationships with loved ones, involvement in the community, continuing previously enjoyed activities, and acquiring new knowledge. In order to discover their own form of self-realization, older people must be influenced by their own level of motivation, personal characteristics, and values [1].

Profile of a social worker working with elderly people. The results of the research revealed three most important qualities of a social worker: empathy, patience, and sincerity. It was emphasized that a social worker must be able to approach each person, understand them, be attentive and flexible, taking each situation individually into account. In addition, one of the most important values of a social worker was identified – humanity (see Table 2).

Table 2

Profile of a social worker working with elderly people

Category	Subcategory
Personal characteristics	Empathy
	Patience
	Sincerity
Abilities	Ability to approach people
	Understanding
	Attentiveness
Values	Flexibility
	Humanity

Research by other authors shows that the most important aspect determining positive results is the social worker's abilities, giving hope, and creating opportunities in the life of an elderly person [10]. This research revealed the most important qualities of a social worker when working with older people: empathy, patience, sincerity, and other qualities. Other authors argue that social workers working with older people must be tolerant, patient, and compassionate, and able to devote a

lot of attention and dedication [12]. This research highlighted the necessary skills of a social worker: the ability to approach people, listen and understand, be attentive and flexible. The most important value of a social worker – humanity – also stood out.

The roles of social workers in providing assistance to older people. The results highlighted three main roles: helper, motivator, and grandchild. However, other roles such as advocate, psychologist, and psychiatrist were also mentioned (see Table 3).

Table 3

Social worker assistance in the self-realization of elderly people

Category	Subcategory
Role in providing assistance	Helper
	Motivator
	The role of the "grandson"
	Other roles

A social worker is a specialist who performs various social work roles and, if necessary, is able to switch between them. A social worker must ensure the performance of mediation, counseling, and case management roles and, in doing so, helps older people to become involved in the community and realize themselves and their needs [13]. This research revealed three main roles of a social worker in providing assistance to older people: helper, motivator, and "grandchild." The roles of advocate, psychologist, and psychiatrist were also mentioned. Other authors argue that social workers become

helpers who seek to reduce the anxiety experienced by older people and restore the balance of their internal resources [3; 13].

Challenges in communicating with elderly people about the meaning of life. The results of the research showed that conversations about the meaning of life depend on the social worker's attitude. Older people do not communicate directly with social workers about the meaning of life, and their communication is limited by their personal limitations (see Table 4).

Table 4

Challenges in communicating with elderly people about the meaning of life

Category	Subcategory
Communication challenges	Appropriate verbal expressions
	Indirect communication about meaning
	Limited opportunities for individuals to communicate

In this research, social workers shared certain situations of service recipients and the interventions applied. Social work is based on theories that focus on the practical application of social systems and personal behavior theories, carrying out interventions where the individual and the environment interact [13]. This research revealed individually tailored social worker interventions that were based on the analysis of service recipients, knowledge, assessment of available resources, and personal strengths. In order to ensure and implement interventions, it is necessary to know the person well as a whole [10]. This research also revealed changes in the interventions used. Interventions were carried out through occupational activities: involving elderly people in senior clubs, dancing, refreshing musical skills, refreshing favorite activities such as sewing, and inviting them to participate in organized occupational activities. The interventions successfully implemented by the social worker created opportunities for older people to actively engage in society, strengthen themselves physically and psychologically, open up to other people and new experiences, and rediscover long-forgotten activities. Other authors argue that social workers practicing gerontological social work must take into account the factors that complicate communication with older people [4].

This research revealed that the main challenges faced by social workers when working with older people are: the personal attitude of the social worker, when the worker feels that they know more than the service recipient. Indirect communication about meaning among older people – people are not inclined to communicate directly about the meaning of life and its importance. Limited communication opportunities due to certain diseases, syndromes, or other changes occurring during the aging process. Therefore, in order to achieve change in a person through social work, the efforts of the social worker alone are not enough. The importance of the social worker's attitude when working with older people is also revealed. Other authors argue that in order to achieve successful intervention, social workers must have a positive attitude towards older people and the ageing process itself [12].

Social worker assistance to a person who feels that life has lost its meaning. The results of the research revealed that social workers respond by being present, communicating, and trying to give hope to the elderly person. However, if the situation does not change, they cooperate with other specialists such as psychologists or other social workers. If the situation takes a turn for the worse, a chaplain is involved (see Table 5).

Table 5

Social worker assistance to a person who feels that life has lost its meaning

Category	Subcategory
Reactions to a person who has lost the meaning of life	Being there
	Communication
	Giving hope
Cooperation with other specialists	Psychologist
	Chaplain
	Other social worker

This research revealed social workers' reactions to individuals who feel they have lost the meaning of life. The reactions are based on individuality, taking into account the needs of the elderly person themselves. The following were identified: the social worker's presence, communication, and giving hope. Other authors argue that social work professionals who focus on service recipients as individuals should assess the individual's attitude and perspective on their personal situation during discussions with elderly people [11]. Other authors' studies have shown that the most important aspect determining positive results is the social worker's ability

to communicate and establish mutual relationships with older people and to give them hope [10]. This research also revealed that social work is based on cooperation with specialists in other fields.

Improving social workers' competencies by enhancing their ability to help older people realize their potential. The results highlighted the following areas for competence improvement: communication skills training, organization of sociocultural activities, opportunities for applying innovations, changes in the health of older people, opportunities for successful aging, and other relevant training (see Table 6).

Table 6

Improving social workers' competencies by enhancing their ability to help older people realize their potential

Category	Subcategory
Areas for improving competencies	Communication skills training
	Organization of sociocultural activities
	Opportunities for applying innovations
	Health changes in older people
	Opportunities for successful aging
	Other relevant training

Social work is one of the professions based on continuous competence development, expansion of various knowledge, discovery of ways to express creativity, finding new and adapting already known work models, and the ability to adapt and ensure comprehensive preparation of specialists in this field in various situations [13]. This research revealed the need for social workers to acquire additional knowledge focused on the self-realization of older people and the discovery of meaning in life. It also highlighted the need to improve communication skills with older people, organize sociocultural activities, expand the range of activities, and develop competencies in engaging and motivating. Other authors reveal that social workers must have a good understanding of gerontology, the social and psychological processes of aging in society, and be familiar with human psychosocial development [12]. This research revealed that social workers need training on the most common diseases, syndromes, and disabilities in old age and how to manage them. Learn more about the theoretical and practical applications of successful aging and other psychology- or pedagogy-based training.

Conclusions

1. The roles of social workers focused on the self-realization of older people are multifaceted and include mediation, counseling, empowerment, advocacy, and community mobilization. These roles contribute to improving the quality of life of older people, strengthening their social participation and dignity. The process

of self-actualization in old age depends not only on individual characteristics, but also on the social environment, so the activities of social workers must be directed both toward providing personal assistance and toward promoting community change.

2. Social workers play an important role in encouraging older people to find purpose, meaning, and fulfillment in their lives. They provide social services and emotional support to help older adults realize their potential. Social workers can also organize activities that promote socialization, activity, and community involvement, thereby encouraging older adults to pursue meaningful goals and find meaning in life. Their role is important because they help older people reveal their unique autobiography, the most important themes of their lives, thus conveying and emphasizing their agency. In various situations, social workers become assistants, consultants, intermediaries, and enablers, seeking to reduce the anxiety experienced by older people, restore their inner resources, and reestablish their balance. The research confirmed the importance of these roles and revealed a new role for social workers—that of a "grandchild" who creates a personal connection with an elderly person and helps to transform past grievances into a feeling of hope.

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